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Properties Of Ceiling Board Produced From Sawdust And Plastic Wastes

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the physical, mechanical, and thermal properties of plastic-sawdust waste composites developed for use as low-cost, sustainable ceiling boards. Varying plastic-to-sawdust mix ratios (1:2, 1:3, 1:4, and 1:5) were evaluated to determine their suitability based on density, water absorption, compressive strength, hardness, thermal conductivity, and thermal resistivity. In Nigeria, particularly in the southern region, the improper disposal of abundant wood sawdust and non-biodegradable plastic waste contributes significantly to environmental pollution, affecting land, air, and water quality. The production of plastic-sawdust ceiling boards was carried out using compression moulding via the melt casting method. Results showed that as sawdust content increased, density and hardness decreased, while water absorption and thermal resistivity increased. The 1:2 and 1:3 ratios recorded densities within the ASTM standard range (350–400 kg/m³), water absorption within the IS3087 (2005) limit of 40%, and compressive strengths that met ASTM requirements (448–868 kPa). Thermal performance improved with higher sawdust content, showing reduced conductivity and enhanced insulation. The study concludes that composites with 1:2 and 1:3 mix ratios provide an optimal balance of structural integrity, moisture resistance, and thermal insulation, making them viable alternatives to conventional ceiling board materials while promoting waste recycling and environmental sustainability.

Keywords: ceiling boards, plastic, sawdust, waste composites

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Waste generation is one of the major threats to the environment. Industrial development, urbanization, and agricultural practices have been highlighted as the major sources of waste in our environment (Young *et al.*, 2010). However, little attention is directed to the wood industries, which have great potential to generate toxic waste into the land, water and air (Harshavardhan and Muruganandam, 2017). Combustion of wood saw dust can generate air pollutants such as CO₂, CH₄, NO_x, SO_x, and other toxic gases (Gimbutaite and Veneckus 2008; IARC, 2006). Wood rich in heavy metals can pollute the soil when it decays or be leached to surrounding water bodies (Sardar *et al.*, 2013). Approaches to wood management vary, but one of the most beneficial approaches is resource recycling, which defines turning wood into a useful product (Harshavardhan and Muruganandam, 2017). One of the most successful approaches to the management of wood sawdust is the production of particle boards from it.

Particle board is a composite wood product of sawdust (and agricultural waste) blended with synthetic resins or organic adhesives and extruded into solid form (Wang and Sun, 2002). Formaldehyde resins

such as amino formaldehyde, urea melamine, and phenol formaldehyde resins have been used for decades in the production of particleboard, but due to their effect on end users, have now been banned (IARC, 2006). However, due to the formation of formaldehyde, carbon monoxide, and hydrogen cyanide, which are carcinogenic, recent research interest is directed to green synthetic routes that will eliminate the generation of toxic materials. The use of starch of plant origin has given hope for the eco-friendly production of particleboard (Kennedy, 1989; Xu et al., 2014). Modified starch adhesives are now used for adhesion of materials because they are safe, nontoxic, grossly underutilized, renewable, and cheap, and exhibit the required characteristics of tack, resistance to moisture, binding strength, and durability. Plastic, on the other hand, is a non-biodegradable waste material. Accumulation of plastic waste is increasing due to an increase in population, urbanization, and development. Many people throw out plastic after using it. It is non-biodegradable and affects the growth of plants. So, vegetation gets affected. It is also harmful to animals when consumed. The reuse of plastic waste in building constructions, industries is considered to be the most practical application. Plastic can be reused in various sectors like marketing, manufacturing, and transportation etc.

1.1 Problem Statement

Waste management becomes more sustainable and profitable when it incorporates resource recovery, reuse, and recycling (Lacovidou et al., 2017). In Nigeria, especially in the southern region, wood sawdust is abundantly available, and its improper disposal has raised significant environmental concerns (Jeong, 2011). Similarly, plastic waste poses serious management challenges due to its non-biodegradability and the environmental hazards associated with its accumulation. The ineffective handling of these waste streams contributes to land, air, and water pollution, further exacerbating environmental degradation.

Utilizing these wastes—particularly plastic and sawdust—in construction applications presents a viable solution aligned with ideal waste management principles. By converting them into useful building materials, such as ceiling boards, this approach not only addresses waste disposal issues but also supports the production of affordable, sustainable, and eco-friendly construction products. Therefore, this research aims to develop ceiling boards using plastic and sawdust as alternative raw materials to replace conventional high-cost ceiling boards, ultimately promoting green construction and environmental sustainability.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

The project aims to assess the properties of the ceiling board produced from sawdust and plastic waste. The main objectives are:

- i. To characterize the plastic waste and the sawdust.
- ii. To develop an efficient way to utilize the plastic and sawdust wastes
- iii. To produce less costly materials in the field of Civil engineering construction.
- iv. To promote effective methods of recycling plastic waste and sawdust.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 History of Ceiling Boards

Some years ago, asbestos was used in the production of ceiling boards, a fibre naturally found in rock formations throughout the world. Its usage was because it has high tensile strength, high resistance to fire, and poor conductivity of heat. However, asbestosis, which causes cancer, is caused by asbestos; as a result, producers of ceiling boards carried out research to find substitute materials to be used in the production of ceiling boards. These substitutes are agricultural wastes, shredded wood, etc. However, the use of shredded wood as reinforcement for inorganic binders points back to the genesis of the nineteenth century (Oladele, 2014).

2.2 Types of Ceiling Boards

There are five different classes of ceiling boards, which are: asbestos cement ceiling board, acoustic ceiling board, gypsum ceiling board, gypsum fibre ceiling board, and cement fibre ceiling board. Classifications are based on the materials used for their production.

Asbestos cement ceiling boards are mainly a product of cement, where about 10 to 15% asbestos is added for reinforcement. The asbestos fibres were coated within; thus, people inside the building with asbestos cement ceiling boards were likely to be safer than people outside in the open space (Olorunmaiye, 2015).

Acoustical ceiling board is a low-waste production process that consists of mineral wool, gypsum, paper, starch, as well as other mixed materials. Ceiling boards that are chipped or broken during the manufacturing process are recycled and returned to the process. (Sheni, 2017)

Gypsum is non-toxic to humans. Gypsum, the primary raw material, occurs naturally like salt or limestone and is one of the most abundant minerals on the planet. Synthetic gypsum is a byproduct or waste material from other manufacturing processes, primarily the desulphurization of flue gases in fossil-fueled power plants and the manufacture of titanium dioxide used in plants. (Sheni, 2017)

The gypsum fibre manufacturing process combines gypsum and cellulose paper fibres to create a variety of high-performance ceiling boards. Specifically, 85% of the content in these ceiling boards comes from post-consumer recycled ceiling boards, and this offers an excellent sustainable alternative to other wood-based ceiling boards (Sheni, 2017)

In general, cement fibre ceiling boards are a 50/50 mixture of cement and wood or other lignocellulose fibres. The cement fibre ceilings do not easily burn but are resistant to termite damage, rotting, and warping. (Sheni, 2017)

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Materials

The following materials were used for the project are as follows;

- I. Saw Dust
- II. Plastic Waste
- III. Glass
- IV. Metal Container
- V. stirrer
- VI. Source of heat
- VII. Paint

3.2 Methods

3.2.1 Sample Collection and Preparation

First, plastic waste was collected and separated from other types of waste. If the plastic waste was wet or contained moisture, it was dried. Then, the dried plastic waste was crushed into small particles, which were further ground into fine particles. The fine plastic particles were heated in a furnace (Bhatti) until they melted into a liquid form. Sawdust was then added to the molten plastic, and the mixture was thoroughly stirred to achieve a uniform blend. A heat-resistant smooth surface, such as a four-cornered glass plate of known dimensions (to prevent adhesion with the mould), was laid flat, with all four sides bordered by angle iron. The mixture was poured onto this surface to form ceiling boards, which were then left to sun-dry under monitored temperature conditions for two days. After drying, the boards were measured and trimmed to a size of 600 mm² (30 cm length × 20 cm width) using a vernier caliper and a meter rule (Ekpunobi et al., 2015) as shown in Figure 1. For this research, ceiling boards were produced using varying material compositions to determine the most suitable mixture. The setup was left to dry for an additional 24 hours before the boards were removed.

3.2.2 Fixing the proportion of plastic and sawdust

For the fabrication, plastic and sawdust were mixed in different proportions, and samples containing different amounts of sawdust were made. Plastic and sawdust were mixed in different ratios, 1:2, 1:3, 1:4, and 1:5. The reason behind taking different proportions of sawdust is to find the optimum proportion that gives the best results. These results were tabulated and graphs plotted. The composite made from these ratios was further investigated for physical, mechanical, and thermal properties.

3.2.3 Characterisation of plastic waste and sawdust

3.2.3.1 Physical Properties Tested

These test methods covered some of the physical properties tests of the new ceiling board produced, and they are: compressive strength, impact strength, hardness, water absorption, density, thermal conductivity, and resistivity. Machines will be used for some property testing,

3.2.3.1.1 Density:

The density of a sawdust composite refers to the mass per unit volume of the material, usually expressed in grams per cubic centimetre (g/cm³) or kilograms per cubic meter (kg/m³) as shown in Equation (1). It is a key physical property that affects the strength, weight, thermal insulation, and sound absorption of the composite.

$$\rho = \frac{m}{v} \quad \dots (1)$$

3.2.3.1.2 Water absorption (WA)

All the samples at the end of soaking in water and before soaking were weighed; the weights were noted (W₂), and (W₁), respectively.

$$WA = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100 \quad \dots (2)$$

Where, WA (%), is the water absorption, W₂ is the final weight of the composite sample after immersion and W₁ is the initial weight composite sample before immersion.

3.2.3.2 Mechanical Properties of plastic waste and sawdust Wastes Composite

3.2.3.2.1 Compressive strength (CS)

The compressive strength of the sawdust-plastic composite samples was evaluated using the Instron 4260 Universal Testing Machine. Each specimen was subjected to an increasing compressive load until failure, and the maximum load was recorded. The compressive strength (CS) was calculated using the formula:

$$Cs = \frac{F}{A} \quad \dots (3)$$

where:

- CS= Compressive strength (N/mm²),
- F = Maximum load applied (N),
- A = Cross-sectional area of the specimen (mm²).

3.2.3.2.2 Impact strength

This measures the amount of energy absorbed by a material during failure. This will be carried out using a Charpy impact testing machine of capacity 300J.

3.2.3.2.3 Hardness strength

Hardness was determined according to ASTM E384-17 (2017). Also, hardness is the resistance of a material to the penetration of its surface. The Rockwell hardness test method can also be used, which consists of indenting the testing materials with a diamond cone indenter [Robert RHE 1994, Vlack IHV. 1975]. It was determined using the relationship:

$$Hv = 1.854 \frac{F}{D^2} \quad \dots (4)$$

Where;

- F =Applied load,
- D2 =is the area of indentation (mm²) and
- Hv is the Vickers Number.

3.2.3.3 Thermal Properties

3.2.3.3.1 Thermal conductivity (K)

This was the quantity of heat (Q) transmitted through a unit thickness (L) in a dimension normal to a surface of Unit Area (A) due to a unit temperature gradient (DT) under steady state conditions and when the heat transfer was dependent only on the temperature gradient. The sample thermal conductivity was determined using Equation (4)

$$k = \frac{L}{A(\Delta T)} \left(\frac{Q}{t} \right) \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

where:

- k** = thermal conductivity (W/m·K),
- Q/t** = heat absorption rate (W),
- L** = thickness of the sample (0.005 m),
- A** = surface area of the sample (0.06 m²),
- T₁** = initial temperature (431 K),
- T₂** = final temperature.

3.2.3.3.2 Thermal resistivity (TR)

This was the reciprocal of thermal conductivity, denoted by Psi, with the unit of Kelvin-meter per watt.

$$\Psi = 1/\kappa$$

Ψ = thermal resistivity

κ = thermal conductivity

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The properties of the sawdust used are as follows.

Water content:	17%
Bulk density:	215kg/m ³
Water absorption:	280%
Specific gravity:	0.26
Colour:	Brownish
% passing 200mic. Sieve:	6.96%

and that of plastic waste

Water content:	0%
Bulk density:	64.25kg/m ³
Water absorption:	0%
Specific gravity:	0.065
Colour:	Grey

Figure 1: Plastic-Sawdust Waste Composites

4.1 Density of Plastic-Sawdust Waste Composites

Table 1 presents the weights and corresponding densities of sawdust and plastic waste composite samples at different mixing ratios (plastic: sawdust). The volume of each composite sample was constant at 0.0003 m³. The density of each sample was calculated using Equation (1)

Table 1. Density of Plastic-Sawdust Wastes Composite

Samples	Ratio	Wt(kg)	Density(kg/m ³)	Average. Density(kg/m ³)
A	1:2	0.111	370.0	-
B	1:2	0.113	376.7	-
C	1:2	0.110	366.7	371.1
A	1:3	0.107	356.7	-
B	1:3	0.109	363.3	-
C	1:3	0.106	353.3	357.8
A	1:4	0.102	340.0	-
B	1:4	0.103	343.3	-
C	1:4	0.102	340.0	341.1
A	1:5	0.098	326.7	-
B	1:5	0.097	323.3	-
C	1:5	0.097	323.3	324.4

Figure 1: Graph of the Density of Plastic-Sawdust Waste Composites

From Figure 1, the results show that as sawdust content increases from a 1:2 to a 1:5 plastic-to-sawdust ratio, the average density of the composite decreases, with the highest density of 371.1 kg/m³ at 1:2 and the lowest at 324.4 kg/m³ for 1:5. This decrease is due to sawdust's lower density and the increased presence of voids during moulding. Notably, the densities at 1:2 and 1:3 ratios fall within the ASTM standard range of 350–400 kg/m³ for ceiling boards, indicating their suitability for structural use

4.2 Water Absorption of Plastic-Sawdust Waste Composites

Table 2 presents the water absorption of plastic-sawdust waste composites

Samples	Ratio	Initial weight(g)	Final weight(g)	Water absorption (%)
A	1:2	640	683.52	6.8
B	1:3	674	744.1	10.4
C	1:4	782.6	894.5	14.3
D	1:5	910.8	1078.4	18.4

Figure 2: Graph of the water absorption rate of plastic-sawdust Waste Composites

The water absorption increases with an increase in the sawdust content, as seen in Figure 2. The observed range is in accordance with IS3087 (2005) recommendation of 40% as the maximum water absorption capacity after 24 hours. Therefore, all the results agree with the standard. However, the variation in water absorption between the produced boards is due to an increase in the sawdust content, which makes the specimens absorb more water.

4.3 Compressive Strength

Table 3. Compressive strength of plastic-sawdust waste composite

Sample	Ratio	Force (kN)	Area of specimen (m ²)	C.S (kN/m ²)	AV. C.S(kN/m ²)
A	1:2	32.4	0.06	540.0	-
B	1:3	36.7	0.06	611.7	-
C	1:4	33.8	0.06	563.3	571.70
A	1:2	35.7	0.06	595.0	-
B	1:3	41.0	0.06	683.0	-
C	1:4	38.6	0.06	643.3	640.43
A	1:2	28.6	0.06	476.67	-
B	1:3	30.0	0.06	500.0	-
C	1:4	30.2	0.06	503.3	493.30
A	1:2	29.4	0.06	490.0	-
B	1:3	24.6	0.06	410.0	-
C	1:4	22.1	0.06	368.3	422.77

Figure 3: Graph of the Compressive Strength of Plastic-Sawdust Waste Composites

The compressive strength of the ceiling board produced increased from 571.70kPa to 640.443kPa and dropped to 422.77kPa at a ratio of 1:5. This shows that ratios 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 are acceptable according to the ASTM standard (448 kPa -868 kPa) while found inadequate at a ratio of 1:5.

4.4 Hardness

Table 4 represents the force applied at different mix ratios of the plastic-sawdust waste composite. A constant area of indentation, **0.06 m²**, was used to determine the hardness of each sample using Equation 4. The Brinell Hardness Number (BHN) was calculated by applying the formula

Table 4: Hardness of the Plastic-Sawdust Waste Composite.

Samples	Mix ratio	Force (N)	Hardness(kN/mm ²)
A	1:2	26.4	0.816
B	1:3	25.9	0.800
C	1:4	24.6	0.7601
D	1:5	22.8	0.7045

Figure 4: Graph of the Hardness Strength of Plastic-Sawdust Waste Composites

Figure 4 shows that the hardness of the plastic-sawdust composite decreases as the sawdust content increases. Samples with higher plastic content, like the 1:2 mix, exhibit greater hardness due to better compaction and surface resistance, while those with more sawdust, such as the 1:5 mix, are softer and less dense. This highlights the trade-off between mechanical strength and material composition.

4.5 Thermal Conductivity (k)

Table 5. Thermal conductivity of plastic-sawdust waste composite

Sample	Ratio	Final Temperature T ₂ (K)	Thermal conductivity (w/m.k)
A	1:2	426.9	0.203
B	1:3	417.5	0.0620
C	1:4	405.7	0.043
D	1:5	391.2	0.021

Figure 5: Graph of the thermal conductivity of plastic-sawdust Waste Composites

In Table 5, it is observed that the thermal conductivity of the plastic-sawdust composites decreases as the proportion of sawdust increases. At a 1:2 plastic-to-sawdust ratio, the composite recorded the highest thermal conductivity of 0.203 W/m·K, while the 1:5 ratio had the lowest at 0.021 W/m·K. This trend shows that higher sawdust content improves the composite’s thermal insulation properties by reducing heat transfer through the material.

4.6 Thermal Resistivity

Table 6: resistivity of plastic-sawdust Waste Composite

Sample	Ratio	Thermal resistivity (M.K.W)
A	1:2	4.93
B	1:3	16.13
C	1:4	23.26
D	1:5	47.62

Figure 6: Graph of the thermal resistivity of plastic-sawdust Waste Composites

From Table 6, which is the reciprocal of thermal conductivity, it is evident that thermal resistivity increases as the sawdust content in the plastic-sawdust composite increases. At a 1:2 plastic-to-sawdust ratio, the thermal resistivity was **4.93 m·K/W**, while the 1:5 ratio recorded the highest value of **47.62 m·K/W**. This trend is consistent with the previously observed thermal conductivity results, where higher sawdust content led to lower thermal conductivity and therefore higher thermal resistivity.

CONCLUSION

The experimental results demonstrate that increasing sawdust content in plastic-sawdust composites significantly influences key physical and mechanical properties. As the sawdust ratio increases from 1:2 to 1:5, the average density decreases due to the inherently lower density of sawdust and the formation of voids during moulding. However, the 1:2 and 1:3 mix ratios meet the ASTM standard range (350–400 kg/m³) for ceiling boards, indicating their structural suitability. Water absorption also rises with higher sawdust content but remains within the IS3087 (2005) limit of 40%, ensuring compliance with moisture performance standards. Compressive strength peaks at the 1:3 ratio (640.443 kPa) and declines at 1:5 (422.77 kPa), making 1:2 to 1:4 ratios acceptable per ASTM guidelines (448–868 kPa). Hardness follows a similar trend, decreasing as sawdust increases, confirming the trade-off between mechanical strength and material content. In terms of thermal performance, higher sawdust content enhances insulation, as reflected by the drop in thermal conductivity and corresponding rise in thermal resistivity. Overall, the 1:2 and 1:3 mix ratios offer the best balance between strength, durability, and insulation, making them ideal for producing cost-effective and sustainable ceiling boards.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study on the production and evaluation of plastic-sawdust composite ceiling boards using the Compression Moulding via Melt Casting Method, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Adoption of 1:2 and 1:3 Mix Ratios: These ratios demonstrated optimal performance in terms of density, compressive strength, hardness, water absorption, and thermal insulation. They are recommended for commercial production due to their compliance with relevant ASTM and IS standards.
- ii. Promotion of Waste Recycling: Government agencies, construction industries, and environmental bodies should support the recycling of plastic and wood sawdust waste for use in building materials to reduce environmental pollution and encourage sustainable construction practices.
- iii. Technology Transfer and Local Production: The method demonstrated is simple and cost-effective. It should be promoted through technology transfer programs, especially in regions with high waste generation and limited access to conventional building materials.

Generally, these recommendations aim to maximize the environmental, economic, and structural benefits of using plastic-sawdust composites as sustainable building materials.

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